

A Complete DECam Survey of Nearby Galaxy Clusters

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The Local Volume Complete Cluster Survey (LoVoCCS) is an NSF's NOIRLab Survey Program to observe all 107 nearby galaxy clusters (those within redshifts $0.03 < z < 0.12$) that are not obscured by the Milky Way and that have X-ray luminosity $L_x > 10^{44}$ erg/s. The X-ray luminosity criterion ensures that all clusters were detected in the X-ray with > 5 sigma significance. LoVoCCS takes advantage of the Victor M. Blanco 4m Telescope's Dark Energy Camera (DECam), which provides ugriz imaging with a depth equivalent to 1st- or 2nd-year LSST depth in each filter. Observations are optimized to uniformly preserve good seeing in the optimal shape measurement filter images. Ian Dell'Antonio (Brown University) is the LoVoCCS principal investigator.

The primary scientific goals of LoVoCCS are to measure the cluster masses and matter distributions at 200 kpc resolution using weak gravitational lensing. This information will be used to determine the relation between the cluster stellar populations, X-ray emitting gas, and dark matter. We will also detect faint and low-surface brightness cluster galaxies, uncover new galaxy-galaxy and galaxy-ICM interactions, and trace the evolution of galaxy properties from the cluster periphery to the center. The archival dataset will also be of great interest to the study of transients in the vicinity of the clusters. Finally, the resolution of the lensing reconstruction and the rest frame wavelength coverage match the expected measurements from WFIRST at $z \sim 0.5$. LoVoCCS will therefore serve

as the low-redshift anchor to the detailed study of the evolution of clusters.

The images for LoVoCCS are being analyzed using the LSST Data Management Science Pipelines of the Vera C. Rubin Observatory. This allows us to make use of recent developments in PSF fitting and weak lensing measurements and additionally ensures that the photometric catalogs and images produced can be used as first-epoch measurements to detect transients in and behind the clusters in the Year 1 LSST data. Data-taking for LoVoCCS is about 20% complete, but the first stacked cluster images and shape and photometric catalogs have already been produced and will be available at the NOIRLab Astro Data Archive site beginning in the third quarter of 2020. Individual community-pipeline-processed exposures are already available for download.

The LoVoCCS collaboration consists of Ranga-Ram Chary (IPAC/Caltech), Doug Clowe (Ohio), Michael Cooper (UC Irvine), Ian Dell'Antonio (Brown, PI), Megan Donahue (Michigan State), Gus Evrard (Michigan), Shenming Fu (Brown), Mark Lacy (NRAO), Tod Lauer (NOIRLab), Binyang Liu (Brown), Jacqueline McCleary (NASA/JPL), Massimo Meneghetti (INAF/Bologna), Hironao Miyatake (Nagoya Univ.), Priyamvada Natarajan (Yale), Elena Pierpaoli (USC), Marc Postman (STScI), Jubee Sohn (SAO), Keiichi Umetsu (ASIAA), Yousuke Utsumi (SLAC/Stanford), and Gillian Wilson (UC Riverside).

Weak lensing surface mass overdensity plot superimposed on the *gri* image of the central $40' \times 40'$ of the LoVoCCS image of Abell 3827, showing the mass concentration centered on the BCG, with extensions to groups to the SE. The peak near the upper left edge of the image corresponds to a much higher redshift cluster and is unrelated to A3827. (Credit: CTIO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/Brown University/LoVoCCS/S. Fu)